

"CORRELATION STUDIES AND PATH COEFFICIENT ANALYSIS IN PIGEONPEA (*Cajanus cajan* (L.) Millsp.)"

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Abstract

The present investigation was carried out for, Correlation Studies and Path Coefficient Analysis in Pigeonpea (*Cajanus cajan*). Correlation studies the characters number of pods per plant, test weight, number of secondary branches per plant, number of seeds per pod exhibited positive and highly significant genotypic correlation with seed yield. This indicates that the simultaneous improvement of these characters through selection. Path coefficient analysis indicated that the characters viz. days to 50 % flowering and plant height exhibited negative direct effect on seed yield per plant. Hence, the selection of genotypes based on these characters as selection criterion would be helpful in improving the seed yield potential of Pigeonpea.

Key words: Pigeonpea, Correlation, Genotypic, Phenotypic, Path coefficient

Introduction

Pigeon pea (*Cajanus cajan* L.) commonly known as gram is the fifth most important food legume crop in the world after soybean, groundnut, dry beans and peas. This crop occupies an essential place in our daily diet as very high-quality source of protein. It is mainly cultivated for its dry seeds and green vegetables in dry areas of the tropics and subtropics. In India pigeonpea grown on an area of 4.45 M. ha with average total production of 4.18 M. tones and productivity about 937 Kg/ha during 2018-19. In Maharashtra during 2018-19 pigeonpea cover the area about 12.20 lakh ha with the production about 10.56 lakh tones and the productivity about 866 Kg/ha (Anonymous, 2019). In marathwada pigeonpea grown on area of 4.46 Lakh ha with average total production of 3.95 lakh tones and productivity about 885 Kg/ha (Anonymous, 2019).

In plant breeding, correlation coefficient analysis measures the mutual relationship between various variables and determines the component characters on which selection can be based for genetic improvement in yield. Correlation coefficient is a statistical measure which is used to find out the degree (strength) and direction of relationship between two or more variables. The phenotypic and genotypic paths are commonly estimated to determine yield contributing characters which are useful for plant breeders and genetics in selection of elite genotypes from diverse genetic population. The association of one or more characters influenced by a large number of genes is elaborated statistically by correlation coefficients. Genotypic correlation coefficient provides a measure of genotypes conjugation between characters. The method of partitioning the correlation into direct and indirect effects by path coefficients analysis was suggested by Wright (1921). It provides useful information on the relative merits of the traits in the selection criteria. Breeder selects the parents on the basis of phenotypic divergence, but for effective breeding, the knowledge of genetic diversity amongst the parents with respect to the characters which are to be improved is essential.

In applied plant breeding, the correlation and path analysis provide information on genetic association of yield and different yield contributing characters, which in turn are useful in developing breeding strategies.

Material And Methods

The present investigation on chickpea for correlation and path analysis was conducted at College of Agriculture, Badnapur, during *kharif* season of 2019-20. Experimental material comprising 100 genotypes lines with wider variability for different characters received from ARS, Badnapur. Hundred genotypes of Pigeonpea were evaluated in a randomized block design with two replications during *kharif* season of 2019-20. Each genotype was sown in two rows of 4 m length with spacing of 90 cm

between rows and 20 cm within rows. The data were recorded on five randomly selected plants of each replication for all characters such as days to 50% of flowering, days to maturity, plant height (cm), number of primary branches per plant, number of secondary branches per plant, number of pods per plant, number of seeds per pod, harvest index, test weight, and seed yield.

Result And Discussion**Correlation coefficients**

In present investigation, the character number of pods per plant, test weight, number of secondary branches, number of seeds per pod recorded highly positive significant with seed yield. Seed yield per plant had highly positive significant correlation with number of pods per plant ($p=0.7033$; $g=0.7088$). Chandirakala and Ravendran (1998) found that the seed yield was significantly and positively correlated with number of pods per plant. In the present study test weight, ($p=0.5773$; $g=0.5980$), number of secondary branches ($p=0.3203$; $g=0.3473$), number of seeds per pod, ($p=0.2483$; $g=0.2388$) was significantly and positively correlated with seed yield. Similar result was found by Niranjana *et al.* (2014), pushpavalli *et al.* (2018), Yerimani *et al.* (2013) for test weight, number of secondary branches, number of seeds per pod. In other words, an increase in the magnitude of these characters would lead to an increase in the magnitude of seed yield.

Path analysis

In path coefficient analysis the characters number of pods per plant, test weight, number of seeds per pod, harvest index, number of secondary branches per plant, days to maturity, number of primary branches per plant had positive direct effect on seed yield in decreasing order of magnitude revealing that these were major yield contributing traits in pigeonpea. Among all the components number of pod per plant exhibited the highest direct effect ($p=0.6581$) on seed yield followed by test weight ($P=0.3948$), number of seeds per pod ($p=0.3006$), harvest index ($p=0.0888$), number of secondary branches per plant ($p=0.0871$), days to maturity ($p=0.0301$), number of primary branches per plant ($p=0.0233$). While, days to 50% flowering ($p=-0.0039$) plant height ($p=-0.0057$) recorded negative direct effect at phenotypic levels. Similar results reported by Thanki and Swargaonkar (2010) for number of pods per plant, seed per pod and test weight.

At genotypic level number of pod per plant exhibited the highest positive direct effect ($g=0.6555$) on seed yield followed by test weight ($G=0.3978$), number of seeds per pod ($g=0.2902$), number of secondary branches per plant ($g=0.0976$), harvest index ($g=0.0972$), days to maturity ($g=0.0294$), number of primary branches per plant ($g=0.0231$), days to 50% flowering ($g=0.0001$). While plant height ($g=-0.0077$) recorded negative direct effect at genotypic level. Similar result reported by Vijayalakshmi *et al.* (2013) for number of seed per pod (0.7493) had direct effect on seed yield in pigeonpea. Rao *et al.* (2013)

reported Genotypic path analysis for number of pods per plant had the high positive direct effect (0.901) on seed yield followed by harvest index (0.651), 100 seed weight (0.498). These findings revealed that these were major yield contributing traits in pigeonpea. Path coefficient indicated that the characters viz., days to 50% flowering, plant height had negative direct effect on seed yield. But these characters had positive indirect effect via. Another character on seed yield. Hence, the selection of genotypes based on these characters as selection criterion would be helpful in improving the seed yield potential of pigeonpea.

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Table.1 Estimation of phenotypic (above diagonal) correlation coefficients in pigeonpea.

Character	Days to 50% flowering	Days to maturity	Plant Height	Number of primary branches/plant	Number of secondary branches/plant	Number of pods /plant	Number of seeds /pod	Test Weight	Harvest index	Seed Yield /plant
Days to 50% flowering	1.0000	0.2702***	0.1303	-0.0129	0.0387	-0.0055	-0.1248	0.0420	0.0048	0.0176
Days to maturity		1.0000	0.1148	0.0374	-0.0370	-0.0273	-0.2194 **	-0.1756 *	0.1336	-0.1153
Plant height (cm)			1.0000	0.0962	0.1065	-0.0307	0.0623	0.1657 *	0.0403	0.0763
Number of primary branches / plant				1.0000	0.0798	0.0738	-0.0677	0.0968	-0.1678 *	0.0824
Number of secondary branches /plant					1.0000	0.2565 ***	0.0083	0.2519***	-0.4220**	0.3203***
Number pods /plant						1.0000	-0.1484 *	0.2158 **	-0.2125**	0.7033***
Number of seeds/ pod							1.0000	0.1076	0.1145	0.2483***
Test weight(g)								1.0000	-0.1093	0.5773***
Harvest index(%)									1.0000	-0.0967

* Significant at 5 % level of probability or level of significance

** Significant at 1 % level of probability or level of significance

Table 2. Estimation of genotypic(above diagonal) correlation coefficient in pigeonpea

Character	Days to 50% flowering	Days to maturity	Plant Height	Number of primary branches/plant	Number of secondary branches/plant	Number of pods /plant	Number of seeds /pod	Test Weight	Harvest index	Seed Yield /plant
Days to 50% flowering	1.0000	0.2853***	0.1300	-0.0278	0.0349	-0.0086	-0.1304	0.0375	0.0133	-0.0170
Days to maturity		1.0000	0.1147	0.0467	-0.0315	-0.0230	-0.2303*	-0.1836*	0.1289	-0.1159
Plant height (cm)			1.0000	0.1165	0.1276	-0.0327	0.0756	0.1603*	0.0444	0.0794
Number of primary branches/plant				1.0000	0.0901	0.0933	-0.0672	0.1040	-0.1983*	0.0962
Number of secondary branches /plant					1.0000	0.2786***	0.0023	0.2826***	-0.4757**	0.3473***
Number pods /plant						1.0000	-0.1569*	0.2294***	-0.2200**	0.7088***
Number of seeds/ pod							1.0000	0.1240	0.1116	0.2388***
Test weight(g)								1.0000	-0.0975	0.5980***
Harvest index (%)									1.0000	-0.1010

Table.3 Direct and indirect effect of yield and its component character on seed yield at phenotypic level

Character	Days to 50% flowering	Days to maturity	Plant Height	Number of primary branches /plant	Number of secondary branches /plant	Number of pods /plant	Number of seeds /pod	Test Weight	Harvest index	Correlation with seed yield/plant
Days to 50% flowering	-0.0039	-0.0011	-0.0005	0.0001	-0.0002	0.0000	0.0005	-0.0002	0.0000	-0.0176
Days to maturity	0.0081	0.0301	0.0035	0.0011	-0.0011	-0.0008	-0.0066	-0.0053	0.0040	-0.1153
Plant height (cm)	-0.0007	-0.0007	-0.0057	-0.0005	-0.0006	0.0002	-0.0004	-0.0009	-0.0002	0.0763
Number of primary branches / plant	-0.0003	0.0009	0.0022	0.0233	0.0019	0.0017	-0.0016	0.0023	-0.0039	0.0824
Number of secondary branches /plant	0.0034	-0.0032	0.0093	0.0070	0.0871	0.0223	0.0007	0.0219	-0.0368	0.3203
Number pods /plant	-0.0036	-0.0180	-0.0202	0.0486	0.1688	0.6581	-0.0977	0.1420	-0.1399	0.7033
Number of seeds/ pod	-0.0375	-0.0659	0.0187	-0.0203	0.0025	-0.0446	0.3006	0.0324	0.0344	0.2483
Test weight(g)	0.0166	-0.0693	0.0654	0.0382	0.0994	0.0852	0.0425	0.3948	-0.0432	0.5773
Harvest index(%)	-0.0176	0.0119	0.0036	-0.0149	-0.0375	-0.0189	0.0102	-0.0097	0.0888	-0.0967

Residual effect = 0.4661 underlined figures indicates direct effect.

Table.4 Direct and indirect effect of yield and its component character on seed yield at genotypic level

Character	Days to 50% flowering	Days to maturity	Plant Height	Number of primary branches /plant	Number of secondary branches /plant	Number of pods /plant	Number of seeds /pod	Test Weight	Harvest index	Correlation with Seed yield/plant
Days to 50% flowering	0.0001	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	-0.0170
Days to maturity	0.0084	0.0294	0.0034	0.0014	-0.0009	-0.0007	-0.0068	-0.0054	0.0038	-0.1159
Plant height (cm)	-0.0010	-0.0009	-0.0077	-0.0009	-0.0010	0.0003	-0.0006	-0.0012	-0.0003	0.0794
Number of primary branches / plant	-0.0006	0.0011	0.0027	0.0231	0.0021	0.0022	-0.0016	0.0024	-0.0046	0.0962
Number of secondary branches /plant	0.0034	-0.0031	0.0125	0.0088	0.0976	0.0272	0.0002	0.0276	-0.0464	0.3473
Number pods /plant	-0.0056	-0.0151	-0.0214	0.0612	0.1826	0.6555	-0.1029	0.1504	-0.1442	0.7088
Number of seeds/ pod	-0.0379	-0.0668	0.0219	-0.0195	0.0007	-0.0455	0.2902	0.0360	0.0324	0.2388
Test weight(g)	0.0149	-0.0730	0.0638	0.0414	0.1124	0.0912	0.0493	0.3978	-0.0388	0.5980